

The Main Diseases Related to Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus: A Scoping Review

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Abstract

Introduction: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic and progressive disease that poses a challenge to global public health. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that approximately 422 million people worldwide suffer from the condition, with a particularly high prevalence in low- and middle-income countries. The main physical complications associated with T2DM include diabetic neuropathy, diabetic retinopathy, and chronic kidney disease. The impact of these complications on an individual's quality of life is significant, often leading to functional disability. Despite widespread recognition of the adverse impacts on the health and quality of life of affected individuals, significant gaps remain in understanding the main complications related to T2DM. **Objective:** To analyze, based on scientific literature, the state of knowledge regarding the main complications associated with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. **Methodology:** This is a scoping review that encompasses the items of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist. The data were presented descriptively, based on the tabulation of the findings. **Results:** Infections emerged as the leading cause of mortality among study participants, followed by cardiovascular diseases. The study documented a high prevalence and/or incidence of macrovascular complications (such as severe peripheral arterial disease) and microvascular complications (such as ulcers in the lower limbs). Furthermore, the most frequently recurring variables related to complications are those associated with the cardiovascular system, particularly hypertension. Findings regarding the lipid profile are highly valuable, as well as the alterations related to peripheral polyneuropathies. **Conclusion:** This work reviewed the main complications associated with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), highlighting its complexity and multifactorial nature. The results reveal that T2DM is associated with various emotional, physical, and social complications that affect patients' quality of life, including cardiovascular diseases, nephropathy, retinopathy, and peripheral neuropathy. These issues are often exacerbated by risk factors such as hypertension and dyslipidemia.

Keywords: *Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Complications, Issue.*

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Introduction

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (DM2) is a chronic and progressive disease that represents a global public health challenge. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that approximately 422 million people worldwide suffer from the condition, with a particularly high prevalence in low- and middle-income countries (Organização Mundial da Saúde, 2016).

DM2 is a complex, multifactorial metabolic disease characterized by chronic hyperglycemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion and action. In addition to metabolic complications, DM2 can lead to a series of health problems, both in physical, emotional and social terms.² It is characterized by high blood glucose levels, resulting from insulin resistance or the inability of the pancreas to produce enough insulin. In addition, diabetes has been associated with a variety of physical, emotional and social complications, including cardiovascular disease, depression and social exclusion (American Diabetes Association, 2020).

The main physical problems associated with DM2 include diabetic neuropathy, diabetic retinopathy and chronic kidney disease. The impact of these complications on the individual's quality of life is significant, often leading to functional incapacity (Forbes, & Cooper, 2013).

With regard to emotional aspects, studies have shown that patients with DM2 have a higher prevalence of psychiatric disorders when compared to the general population. Depression and anxiety are the most common of these disorders (Anderson, et al., 2001). The challenges of managing the disease can also lead to emotional stress and reduce adherence to treatment (Gonzalez, et al., 2008).

In the social sphere, DM2 can affect an individual's ability to work and carry out daily activities. In addition, the stigma associated with the disease can lead to social isolation (Schabert, et al., 2013). There is still much to be explored about the social impacts of DM2, which highlights the need for more studies in this area.

Despite widespread recognition of the adverse impacts on the health and quality of life of affected individuals, significant gaps remain in the understanding of the main problems related to DM2.

This study aims to analyze the main problems associated with DM2, considering emotional, physical and social complications. In particular, it seeks to identify gaps in current knowledge on the subject and highlight areas that require greater attention and research.

Methodology

This is a scoping review that takes into account the items in the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist.¹⁸ Observational studies (cohort, case-control and cross-sectional) and randomized clinical trials reporting complications associated with DM2 from 2014 to 2024 were included. Review publications, letters to the editor and papers with aspects similar to those mentioned were not considered.

To identify relevant studies, a systematic search was carried out in electronic databases, including PubMed, Embase, Web of Science, Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), Latin American and Caribbean Health Sciences Literature (Lilacs), PsycINFO.

The search strategy was based on the acronym PCC, in which the target population was patients with DM2, in the context of their main problems.¹⁹ The central research question was: "What are

the main problems associated with DM2, considering emotional, physical and social complications?”. Keywords and MeSH terms related to “Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus”, AND “complications”, OR “harms” were used in the search.

The selection of studies was conducted in two phases. In the first phase, two independent reviewers assessed the titles and abstracts of the studies identified by the search. In the second phase, the same reviewers assessed the full text of the studies selected in the first phase. Discrepancies were resolved by consensus or by a third reviewer.

Data was extracted using a standardized form which included information on the author(s), year of publication, study site, study design and sample characteristics. Demographic variables: age: to assess how DM2 disorders vary in different age groups. Gender: significant differences in problems between men and women. Clinical and laboratory variables: time since diagnosis: whether the duration of diabetes influences the severity of complications; glucose levels: to investigate the relationship between glucose levels and the incidence of complications; body mass index (BMI): to assess how body weight is associated with complications; glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c); estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR). Psychosocial variables: mental health: to investigate the association between psychological conditions (depression, anxiety) and DM2 complications.

Results

A total of 2,128 articles were identified in the databases (PubMed, Embase, Web of Science, Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), Latin American and Caribbean Health Sciences Literature (Lilacs). After removing duplicates, 33 articles were left to read the titles and abstracts, from which 25 articles were chosen, most of them from the United States.

It was found that the most repeated complication variables were those related to the cardiovascular system, especially hypertension. The findings on the lipid profile are of great value, as are the alterations surrounding peripheral polyneuropathies.

Other noteworthy findings include renal function, based on serum creatinine levels and estimated glomerular filtration rate. Data on the psychosocial repercussions of type 2 diabetes mellitus is scarce and incipient.

The samples indicated a profile of patients with obesity (grade I), over 60 years of age and with glycemic control of around 7% of glycated hemoglobin.

Infections emerged as the main cause of mortality among study participants, followed by cardiovascular diseases with a predominance of macrovascular diseases such as peripheral obstructive arterial disease and microvascular diseases such as coronary heart disease.

Discussion

DM2 is a chronic condition that represents a major challenge for public health worldwide. Its prevalence has been increasing and we have seen a lack of knowledge on the part of the population, a lack of knowledge on the part of health managers, a lack of coordination between the federal health care bodies and a progressive increase in public health costs resulting from the treatment of diabetes complications (Organização Mundial da Saúde, 2016).

The human and financial cost of this complication is immense, but simply making the authorities and the community aware of the need for good control of the disease and implementing relatively simple measures can curb this reality. The Brazilian Diabetes Society says: “Diabetes is being considered a disease of epidemic proportions worldwide, with an increasing number of new cases

diagnosed each year. The Brazilian reality lacks: information about the disease and its complications, awareness of the importance of diabetes in public health, adequate training for health professionals, resources, medicines, mentality and political will to tackle the problem effectively.

Diabetes affects 7.6% of the Brazilian population aged between 30 and 69, reaching figures close to 20% in the population over 70. Half of all people with diabetes have the disease and don't know it, since it progresses silently, without producing any major symptoms, and can only be identified when one of its chronic complications arises.

Diabetes affects everyone, adults and children, men and women, rich and poor, any race or creed, without distinction. One of the main problems associated with DM2 is the development of various complications that can be debilitating or even fatal. These complications include cardiovascular, kidney, eye and nerve diseases (Schabert, et al., 2013; American Diabetes Association, 2018).

The quality of current treatment falls far short of what is desirable, indicating an urgent need to adopt educational measures for both health professionals and the community.

Cardiovascular diseases are the main causes of death in people with DM2, accounting for more than half of all deaths in this population. The risk of coronary heart disease is two to four times higher in people with DM2 than in the general population (Emerging Risk Factors Collaboration, 2010).

Diabetic nephropathy is another serious complication of DM2 and is one of the main causes of end-stage renal failure. Approximately 20-40% of patients with DM2 develop this complication (Andersen, et al., 2015).

Diabetic retinopathy and diabetic neuropathy are also frequent complications of DM2. Diabetic retinopathy is the leading cause of blindness among adults of working age in many developed countries (Yau, et al., 2012). Diabetic neuropathy affects up to half of patients with DM2 and can lead to lower extremity amputations (Boulton, et al., 2005).

DM2 is a chronic disease that affects the way the body metabolizes glucose, the main cellular fuel. The complications resulting from DM2 are many and varied, affecting practically every system in the body (American Diabetes Association, 2018).

The cardiovascular system is one of the most affected by DM2. Chronic hyperglycemia contributes to the formation of atheromatous plaques in the arteries, leading to coronary artery disease, as well as increasing the risk of myocardial infarction and stroke (Danaei, et al., 2011). Other cardiovascular complications include heart failure and hypertension.

Diabetic nephropathy is another common complication of DM2. Damage to the small blood vessels in the kidneys can lead to chronic kidney failure and the eventual need for dialysis or a kidney transplant (Alicic, Rooney, & Tuttle, 2017). Approximately 25% of patients with DM2 develop diabetic nephropathy (Tuttle, et al., 2014).

Diabetic retinopathy is one of the main causes of blindness in adults in developed countries. Chronic hyperglycemia damages the blood vessels in the retina, leading to progressive vision loss (Yau, et al., 2012).

Diabetic neuropathy is a complication that affects the peripheral nerves, causing pain and loss of sensation in the extremities, especially the feet. This can lead to the development of ulcers and infections which, in severe cases, may require amputation (Boulton, et al., 2005; Pop-Busui, et al., 2017). Arteriosclerosis is more severe, more diffuse and more distal in diabetics. The prevalence of Peripheral Obstructive Arterial Disease in diabetics is 20% over the age of 40 and 29% over the age of 50. Approximately 85% of diabetics with chronic foot wounds progress to amputation, and

of these, half will suffer a new amputation within two to three years. Between 5-15% of diabetic patients will suffer an amputation at some point in their lives. Three-year survival is 50% after amputation.

The chance of diabetics suffering an amputation is 15 times higher than in the non-diabetic population. Diabetic neuropathy is associated with an increased risk of foot ulcers and is present in 30 to 70% of patients. Neuropathy is present in 70 to 100% of diabetic patients with ulcers.

With the global prevalence of DM2 increasing every year, the problems associated with the disease are of great public health importance (Zimmet, et al., 2016). Chronic hyperglycemia, characteristic of DM2, is associated in the long term with dysfunction and failure of various organs, especially the heart, kidneys, eyes and nerves (American Diabetes Association, 2014).

Data indicates that physical complications, such as diabetic nephropathy and cardiovascular disease, are prevalent among patients with DM2. Studies 20-25 show that 16.4% of patients had coronary heart disease, while 14.6% had a history of cerebral vascular disease. These findings are consistent with previous studies (The Emerging Risk Factors Collaboration, 2010) highlighting the relationship between T2DM and increased cardiovascular risk, suggesting that early interventions and effective management strategies are essential to mitigate these risks, also highlighted by the American Diabetes Association (2018) and the International Diabetes Federation (2019).

In addition to clinical/physical complications, the literature touches on an impact on the emotional and social dimensions of patients' lives. Other studies 6 - 10 reveal that many individuals with DM2 face emotional challenges, such as depression and anxiety, which can be exacerbated by the management of the disease and its complications. The interrelationship between mental health and DM2 is an aspect that is often overlooked, but is crucial for the holistic treatment of patients (Dambha-Miller, 2019; Zhao, 2023)

Another relevant point is the variation in the problems associated with DM2 in different age groups and between genders, as discussed in Narasimhan, & Weinstock, (2014) and Forbes, & Cooper, (2013). The analysis of demographic data suggests that men and women can present complications differently, which implies the need for personalized treatment approaches. The literature reviewed also suggests that ethnic factors can influence the prevalence and severity of complications, which requires special attention in multicultural contexts.

Several studies reinforce the importance of effective glycemic control as a cardiovascular risk factor (Emerging Risk Factors Collaboration, 2010; Yau, et al., 2012; Lundqvist, 2023; American Diabetes Association, 2018). Data indicate that the average pancreatic volume is 33% smaller in individuals with DM2 compared to the control group, which may have significant implications for endocrine function and glucose regulation. In addition, a comparison between different classes of drugs for the treatment of DM2 showed that, despite small variations in the rates of cardiovascular disease, there were no significant differences in outcomes such as hypertension and dyslipidemia between the treated groups (Zhao, 2023). This suggests that the choice of treatment should be individualized, taking into account the patient's characteristics and the presence of comorbidities.

Glycemic control had a significant impact on reducing adverse clinical events, especially in populations with poor glucose control (Lundqvist, 2023). This emphasizes the need for personalized management strategies and the importance of early interventions to prevent serious complications. Patient education and self-care are essential components of successful treatment, enabling individuals to manage their condition more effectively.

The identification of complications such as diabetic neuropathy and retinopathy, which directly affect patients' quality of life, highlights the need for regular monitoring and early interventions (Ofstad, 2017) Neuropathy, for example, can lead to mobility problems and increase the risk of

falls, while retinopathy can result in vision loss, impacting the patient's ability to carry out daily activities. Therefore, regular screening for these complications should be a priority in the management of DM2.

As for microvascular complications, both nephropathy and diabetic retinopathy have been identified as significant. Around 40% of patients with DM2 develop diabetic nephropathy, one of the main causes of end-stage renal failure.³⁰ Furthermore, nephropathy is associated with a significant increase in the risk of all-cause death and cardiovascular mortality in patients with DM2 (Ong, 2021; Nomura, 2021; Lin, 2022; Simmons, 2017; Odnoletkova, 2014; Schrieks, 2018).

Endothelial dysfunction is a crucial phenomenon in the course of cardiovascular disease (CVD) that precedes structural changes in blood vessels and clinical manifestations. It is a condition typically characterized by a reduction in the bioavailability of endothelium-derived relaxing factors (EDRF) such as NO with a concomitant increase in the release of endothelium-derived contracting factors (EDCF) such as endothelin1, causing a reduction in endothelium-mediated vasodilation (Zhang, 2024; Bancks, 2021; Rossing, 2023; Rise Consortium, 2018; Haas, 2019). In addition, there is exacerbated activation of proinflammatory, proliferative and procoagulant mechanisms in all stages of CVD (Groen, 2014; Macauley, 2015; Grade Study Research Group, 2022; The Emerging Risk Factors Collaboration, 2010; Anderson, et al., 2001; Grigsby, et al., 2002; American Diabetes Association, 2018; Stratton, et al., 2000; Tervaert, et al., 2010; Afkarian, et al., 2016; Esper, et al., 2006; Turner, , Belch, & Khan, 2008).

It's clear that the population needs to be educated about DM2, as approximately 25% have the disease and don't know it. In Brazil, there is still a lack of knowledge among managers about the seriousness, extent and cost of DM2 and its complications, a lack of knowledge about the value of prophylactic care, the inability of “temporary” managers to maintain long-term educational and prophylactic actions, a lack of knowledge among managers, patients and their families and, frequently, members of health teams about the diabetic foot “problem”, misallocation of the already scarce existing resources (opting for supply rather than demand), projects centered around the “problem” of diabetic foot, centralized projects with minimal resolution capacity, a greater impact on populations with low incomes and little capacity to mobilize, a chasm between primary care and other levels of care, misinformation on the part of non-specialist doctors themselves, directing specialists towards high complexity and difficulties in the joint action of the various specialties involved in diabetic care.

Although the results of this study provide a comprehensive view of the complications associated with DM2, it is important to recognize some limitations. The possibility of publication bias should be considered, since studies with negative results may not have been published. Future studies should seek greater standardization in definitions and methodologies to facilitate comparisons and generalizations of results.

The results of this study reinforce the need for a multidisciplinary approach to the management of DM2, which considers not only the physical complications, but also the emotional and social aspects that affect patients. Implementing integrated care programs can be an effective strategy for improving health outcomes and quality of life for individuals affected by DM2. Ongoing research is essential to deepen understanding of the associated disorders and develop more effective interventions.

Conclusion

The study highlights the complexity and multifactoriality of DM2. The results show that it is associated with various complications that affect patients' quality of life, including cardiovascular disease, nephropathy, retinopathy and peripheral neuropathy. These problems are often aggravated by risk factors such as hypertension and dyslipidemia.

The effective management of DM2 must go beyond glycemic control, incorporating the management of comorbidities, an educational plan and awareness-raising, especially with regard to possible preventive strategies. Early diagnosis and individualized treatment are crucial, with a multidisciplinary approach for more holistic care.

Coordinated public health strategies are needed to prevent and control DM2, involving health professionals, educators and policymakers. Continued research is vital to improve patient management and quality of life, as well as to develop more effective interventions. Once the clinical picture of the disease has been established, it is essential to be equipped to deal with the main related problems.

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